

ISSN (E): 2181-4570

USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS TO DEVELOP STUDENTS' SOCIO-CULTURAL COMPETENCE THROUGH MULTIMEDIA DEVICES

Askarova G.X

**An English language teacher at the Military Institute of Information
Communication Technologies and Signals**

ABSTRACT

The article deals with the issue of the usage of multimedia devices in developing socio-cultural competence of students. The article describes the creation of e-books and its requirements of implementing in teaching foreign language process. Particularly, harmonious implementation of electronic textbooks in full traditional lessons in the context of independent learning results in intensified learning. As a result, today there is an opportunity for every pedagogue to introduce modern pedagogical technologies into the teaching process. The use of various interactive methods can lead students to become active participants in the learning process.

Key words: competence, socio-cultural, technique, technology, electronic textbooks, motivation, psychological, intensification.

INTRODUCTION

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from February 7, 2017 "On Strategy for Strategy for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", No. UP-4947 of April 20, 2017 "On measures for further development of higher education system". PQ-2909 Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan from May 8, 2013 No 124 "About approval of the state educational standard of foreign languages on continuous education" and other normative-legal acts according to which we have to prepare our young people, who are confidently stepping into the international community, in a comprehensively competent manner.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A.Gurkina, M.V.Dubova, R.S.Arefev, N.I.Arshinova, S.A.Balandin S.B.Belakon, L.A.Borxodoev, T.I.Gustomyasova, IA.Zimnyaya, O.Y.Pestretsova, M.Veliverstova, N.S.Sukhova, O. Khalupo, and I. Shevshshinova investigated the issues of preparation of future foreign language teachers in Russia. Application of modern technologies in foreign language teaching, competence and professional approach very completely-studied in the works of V.V. Safonova, A.A. Ter- Minasova,

ISSN (E): 2181-4570

E.V. Miloserdova, G.V.Elizarova, N.V.Eluhina, M.M.Abdurazakov, A. A. Magomedova, VI Zakharova, B.I.Xasan, M.V.Dubova, N.I. Arshinova. The issues of foreign language leaching skills were investigated by Xartoya, Zang Zen Xenich, T.B. Frayer, J.T. Say, Mari Dakovska, A. Braun, M. Channel, M. Svane's scientific works.

METHODOLOGY

The modern lesson is that today it is important to understand the lessons learned based on world-wide experience using the latest modern information technologies. Particular attention should be paid to the outcomes of teaching, ie, the ability of students to master theoretical knowledge and at the same time have sufficient practical skills, such as the ability to apply the theoretical knowledge in practice, and in particular the formation of self-learning skills of students. Competence-based approach in education implies the ability of students to apply the existing knowledge and skills in the practical experience. As it is known, thousands of interactive teaching methods in the field of pedagogy have been developed and introduced into the learning process, each one being used in its own right and in the optimal situation. Based on our research, we have created the following new interactive techniques that are effective for the development of students' socio-cultural competence.

The "Illustrative intelligent attack" method ("Image Brainstorm")

While this new method, which is being proposed in our study, is similar to the previously known "Intelligence Attack," the method of Illyustrativ Intelligent Attack is uniquely grounded in the principle of transparency. This principle is important in the development of socio-cultural competence of students.

The aim of the method: To identify and develop students' abilities to master the characters and symbols of strangers on the basis of the learned material.

Methods of implementation of the method:

1. Students are given a picture without an explanation. The picture should reflect the history of the country learning the language, the way of the people's lifestyle, and the national traditions (see Picture 1).

ISSN (E): 2181-4570

Picture 1.

2. Students will be asked to provide comments and feedback on the objects/subjects listed above. They need to justify their point of view. When all students express their opinions, the picture above is asked for what and who they are, and students receive oral answers.

3. At the final stage of the study, students are divided into groups of smaller (3-4 people), and by using the Internet, they try to collect as much information as possible about the image and objects/subjects listed above. The assignment is 15 minutes.

4. Groups read their facts. Students will be evaluated according to the number and content of the facts.

Method of "Fake Wikipedia"

This method helps students determine the extent to which they study. National-cultural characteristics of the countries studied during the course. For example, the text you are going to provide will be mixed and misleading about the history, the daily lifestyle and the national customs of the two countries.

Purpose of the course: To develop the students' critical thinking abilities, to determine the degree of their appraisal, to increase the general scientific potential of the subject.

Steps of implementation of the method:

1. Students are given two separate papers on the subject. In one of the texts, there is no error, and the other contains mixed and distorting information.
2. Students are grouped into groups. Annex I applies to each group.
3. Within 25 minutes, each group will be required to identify in writing the errors in the text and provide the correct options. Internet access is permitted during assignment.

4. Students submit their own answer sheets. Thereafter, Annex 2 is added to each group. The errors contained in Appendix 1 are to be corrected.

5. Groups will be evaluated based on the number of errors.

The method of "Country's Fame"

The next proposed methodology is that the students are well versed in their knowledge of the national traditions, art and culture of the studied language.

Purpose of the method: To determine the current level of social life of the students studying in the country, their famous people and their role in national culture.

Steps of implementation of the method:

1. The audience in the audience is released in circles. The tutor also fills the circle.

2. Explains the meaning of the method to the students, for example, briefly describes a person who is already popular in the countries where the teacher has discussed in the lessons. Students are asked questions about that person. (Do you know him? Are you aware of his work?)

3. Then, students are required to do the same. The choice of the famous person is handed over to the student.

4. After each student speaks, the group debate begins. All of them express their opinion about the famous person. (During the interview you can use the requisite, for example, a tennis ball to determine the sequence of students, which will be passed to the next speaker from the student who said the requisite)

5. At the end of the method, all of the celebrities are selected by two groups, then the group is divided into two groups and each group is assigned by one of the two famous people selected by the teacher.

6. Preparing presentations about the group is given as a home duty.

The method of "the word of the day"

The use of this new method of research in our study will bring about key words and concepts on the topic activated by students in the types of speaking activities.

Purpose of the course: To introduce the most important concepts of the subject into the minds of students, to ensure that the subject is fully utilized.

Steps of implementation of the method:

1. At the beginning of the lesson the teacher writes the main words and concepts related to the topic on the board.

2. During the lesson, when the teacher speaks of the subject, he uses the concepts of the board as many times as possible, and again explains to students that these words are the word of the day.

3. Students will be given additional points for their use of the "Day Word" in all the assigned tasks.

4. This method will also be used in conjunction with other methods.

The method of "Die Breast"

The proposed new method serves as an additional tool for the instructor to achieve the goal of the teacher by identifying and eliminating unnecessary aspects of the subject.

Purpose of the course: To define concepts which are hard to master among students.

Steps of implementation of the method:

1. Students are subdivided into smaller groups. A4 format paper is distributed to students.

2. It is desirable to write the concepts that are difficult to master during the lesson.

3. It is necessary to write only the group number on the paper, and the student plays an important role in the full coverage of the concepts that he cannot understand.

4. The paper will be collected, examined, and repetition exercises and assignments will be provided to the students in order to deepen all written concepts.

5. Then the task in paragraph 2 shall be restored.

6. Results are compared.

Method of "Shared Movement"

This new method is designed to help students develop their skills and share their knowledge of others.

The aim of the method is to increase students' common scientific and cultural competence.

1. Stages of Method:

2. Each student is given a clear A5 format leaflet.

3. On one side of the sheet, "Share" is written as "Care" and the name of the owner of the listing is recorded.

4. Each student writes, explains, writes, explains, explains what he/she is reading in the course of the paper's "Share" section, and is a complete, clear and understandable element. (Short and long)
5. Then he passes his leaf to another student, and he accepts it from him.
6. Looks at the "Share" section of the received page, where the student writes, explains, and changes the leaflet to "Care" if the student does not understand it.
7. The leaflets are returned to the owners after writing 4 comments on the "Care" side of each sheet.

We have come to the conclusion that in the process of English language learning, equally balanced teaching of the social and cultural aspects of the country's history, national lifestyle, national traditions and the national traditions in the development of students' socio-cultural competitiveness will bring good results. In the development of students' socio-cultural competence, we paid special attention to the development of effective training and assignments in this direction on the basis of new methods developed within our research. This exercise and assignment system is intended for use in faculties of pedagogical education. The second stage is for "Country Studies" and 3rd year students for "Intercultural communication in teaching foreign languages".

In particular, in the direction of development of socio-cultural competence of students through the history training, the following exercise system can be used:

Working in small groups. Students will be shown an audio recording of the story about the great Amir Temur, the great Alexander, Julius Caesar, and Vincent Chercil. ("Country Study" e-book. "Famous People.") The student uses the "Maslou pyramid" method to identify the historical and cultural significance of four great people, as well as on the basis of the text (see Picture 2):

Picture 2.

When listening to texts, students are given the following information to fill in the following table (see Table 1):

Table 1. Information about famous people

Historical persons	Origin	Outstanding features	Achievements	Contribution to the cultural prosperity
Tamerlane				
Alexander the Great				
Caesar				
Winston Churchill				

Students are given the task of covering socio-cultural life of the people during the period of the great people mentioned above. They show the differences between past and present in this process. Students will be connected to the Internet and will be

contacted by other historical sources. In the course of the task, students will exchange information using the "Shared" method.

The use of the symbols of the British and American symbols on the teaching of state symbols for 2nd year students ("Country Study" electronic text, "Symbols" assignment Picture 3):

Picture 3. The symbols of Great Britain and USA.

Look at the symbols. Which countries are they? What do you know about them? How do you think the symbols are specific? "The student's answer to this question is as follows: Students are divided into two subgroups, discussing the main state symbols of Uzbekistan, the United States and Wales (Britain). Because of the lack of explanation in the pictures, the discussion is based on the method of "Illyustrativ intelligent attack". The small group compares the symbols and guesses their outlook and views in the socio-cultural life of the countries through symbols. Comments are summarized in small groups. Then the essence and meaning of the state symbols presented by the teacher are read out. The information provided by small groups will be checked for the correct or incorrect data and the winner will be identified. This will give students the opportunity to learn about the history of the countries and the social and cultural life of their peoples.

DISCUSSION

Effective use of educational technologies in the learning process of the students on the basis of intercultural cooperation and the development of social cultural competence in foreign language (ensuring the interaction of the teacher with the students in the process of organizing, coordinating and responding to the learning process); the use of interactive techniques in practical exercises will help activate the learning process, increase the interest in the knowledge and intrinsic motivation.

RESULTS

Students used the audio texts of the electronic textbooks independently. The effectiveness of the education of students was monitored on a regular basis. First of all, the interest of the experimental group to the knowledge gained increased. The students' performance has improved. When responding to students' questionnaires, they explained this as follows: the teacher felt that they were being treated individually; the computer repeatedly serves as a patient teacher; easy to master pronunciation of new words based on listening comprehension; automatic delivery of new words and phrases within each exercise will increase their linguistic wealth. The collected data were analyzed to reflect the beliefs of the participants on their ability in developing socio-cultural competence.

CONCLUSION

Hold a modern lesson today is important to understand the lessons based on worldwide experience using the latest modern information technologies. Particular attention should be given to the result of teaching, i.e. to the ability of students to master theoretical knowledge and to have sufficient practical skills, such as the ability to apply the theoretical knowledge in practice, and in particular to the formation of students' independent learning abilities. Competency-based approach in education implies the ability of students to apply their existing knowledge and skills in the practical experience.

Students will have the opportunity to independently take on online assignments in electronic textbooks. The exercises performed in the auditorium are further enhanced through interactive techniques. Through the use of multimedia tools, the students will be able to choose the subject matter autonomous materials in the development of their socio-cultural competencies, and will have the opportunity to work independently on the online training system, the online testing system and audio/video content.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to express our thankfulness to the administrative and professor-teacher staff of Uzbekistan state university of world languages. Samarkand State institute of foreign languages, Navoi state pedagogical institute and Nukus state pedagogical institute as well.

ISSN (E): 2181-4570

We also appreciate the faculty students' efforts who observed lessons held by most experienced teachers of above mentioned institutions and made presentation to share with their findings.

REFERENCES

1. *Sayidaxmedov N. Pedagogik amaliyotda yangi texnologiyalarni qo'llash namunalari -Toshkent RTM, 2000 -46 b.*
2. *Makhkamova G. T. Culture Matters. Tashkent: "Tafakkur Qanoti". 2011-7p.*
3. *Omonov H.T. Xo'jayev T.X. Pedagogik texnologiyalar va pedagogic mahorat. Toshkent "Iqtisod-Moliya" 2009 -39 b.*
4. *Ефременко В.А. Применение информатионных технологий на уроке иностранного языка В.А. Ефременко// Иностранные языки в школе 2007-N68-С. 18-21*

